

NEOSUCCESS

Upscaling and Market Introduction of
Simultaneous Biogas Upgrading and Bio-
Succinic Acid Production

D6.2

DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION PLAN

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Additional author(s) and contribution	
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of the deliverable 6.2 is to outline the path for the most optimal strategy for the dissemination and communication of the NEOSUCCESS Project, focusing on its results and its expected impact in the society and environment. The plan covers the actions to be carried out during the 36 months period of the Project duration and settles the basis for its future development and exploitation.

Main topics discussed in this document are:

- *Internal Communication Protocols.*
- *External Communication Protocols.*
- *Communication Tools.*
- *Target Audiences and messages.*
- *Dissemination actions through different channels.*

This document also aims to create a reference framework and guidelines for the project to achieve the highest visibility, accessibility, market penetration and promotion of its results. Final purpose of Dissemination is to find potential clients for NEOSUCCESS project' products.

1. INTRODUCTION

NEOSUCCESS project aims to build the first plug-and-play industrial solution integrating complementarily two complex processes, which are biogas upgrading into biomethane and fermentation-based biosuccinic acid production, thus obtaining two bio-based valuable products for the industry.

The basis of this breakthrough and patented technology relies on the use of a bacterial strain with the ability to fix the CO₂ contained in the biogas (thus upgrading it to biomethane) and to concomitantly metabolize the sugars present in organic wastes of different typology to produce second-generation succinic acid (SA) as part of a mixed-acid fermentation, resulting in a secure and clean-energy new biological process.

NEOSUCCESS technology comprises a first-of-a-kind solution for biogas industries that fits perfectly the operational workflow of these plants and covers their needs, which are connected to the growing demand for bio-based products, energy and/or fuels with low carbon footprint. Thus, this innovative solution fosters the transition towards a bio-based economy, aligned with the recent Circular Bioeconomy Strategy of the EU. Due to its dimensions, NEOSUCCESS technology will be containerized, thus exhibiting versatile production capacities ranging from 10,000 to 100,000 Nm³/year of biomethane and 35 to 350 t/year of bioSA. The technology is already proved at lab and demonstration scale and will be subjected to a fine-tuning step along this Fast-Track-to-Innovation project to reach the market and comply with purity requirements. In this regard, minimum purities of 95% and 80% will be reached for biomethane and bioSA, respectively.

Figure 1 - NEOSUCCESS merged Biogas and sugar-rich organic wastes into BioMethane and BioSuccinic production process

The overall objective of this Fast-Track-to-Innovation (FTI) project is to build the first industrial NEOSUCCESS unit with a throughput of at least 12,000 Nm³ of biomethane/year and 47,000 kg of bioSA/year, and prove it in an industrial operation environment to reach the market readiness (TRL 9) by the end of the project, along with the creation of a potential client's network to assure a smooth market uptake.

2. OBJECTIVES & SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document is the Deliverable 6.2 “Dissemination and Communication Plan (from here onwards, the D&C Plan) of the Work Package 6 “Dissemination and Communication activities” of the NEOSUCCESS Project (WP6). NORVENTO as the WP 6’ leader, oversees the definition of this plan and the coordination of the different actions involved. It is worth to note that the scope of the D&C Plan includes the identification of potential target markets and stakeholders, thus Norvento takes an important role in the design and implementation of this plan, being the Consortium member that takes care of the commercial-focused tasks of the project.

The **Deliverable 6.2** is closely related to other Deliverables of the Work Package 6:

- **D6.1: NEOSUCCESS website with information about the NEOSUCCESS project, outcomes, results, meetings, etc. (M3).** It is essential to convey the most important concepts and ideas in order to reach through this online tool the highest number of potential stakeholders. The message transmitted on it must be concise and clear.
- **D6.3: First year of the D&C plan implementation (M12).** This report will highlight the execution of all the milestones, activities and fundamental actions that have been designed in the present deliverable during the first year of the NEOSUCCESS project. It will act as a first check point to evaluate D&C Plan and help adopting any corrective actions (if needed) to improve the dissemination and communication procedures.
- **D6.4: Final report on D&C activities (M36).** This deliverable will summarize all the results of the present plan, the accomplishment of its goals and guidelines for the future market exploitation.
- **D6.5: Report on demonstration activities (M36).** This report will be focused on the demonstration activities that, during the lifespan of the project, will be performed to spread the project among stakeholders.
- **D6.6: Training Session Materials and On-Line training tool (M36).** This report will include the information that will be used during training sessions and regarding the special design training tool that will be available online on the NEOSUCCESS project official website.
- **D6.7: Report on the participation on the Open Research Data Pilot (M36).**

2.1 THE NEOSUCCESS’ CONSORTIUM

The NEOSUCCESS’ Consortium is integrated by 4 members and 2 subcontractors. Each of the involved parts has a key role during the project and after it in relation to the Dissemination of results.

Partner		Role during the NEOSUCCESS’ project	Role after the NEOSUCCESS’ project	WP6 effort (D&C)
	IVEM (Coordinator) Spanish WWTP management firm	Construction of the industrial unit and validation in their premises (WWTP).	Design the electromechanical system (software control) and annual maintenance service.	16

Partner		Role during the NEOSUCCESS' project	Role after the NEOSUCCESS' project	WP6 effort (D&C)
	NORVENTO Spanish engineering firm, biogas plant construction	Downstream process upscaling and support on industrial validation. Communication activities, and commercial & scalability strategy.	Commercialisation, construction, installation, and start-up of the NEOSUCCESS technology.	6.50
	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet DTU Dep. of Environmental Engineering	Patent owner (key know-how) R&D support on scaling up.	R&D support on scaling up. Patent licencing to industry partners.	4.00
	AUTH Greek School of Agriculture	Downstream processing prototype + upscaling at industrial site.	R&D support on the downstream processing.	3.00
Subcontractor 1 BIOTECH PRO (DK) , spin-off of DTU		Support for the commercialisation strategy in Northern EU, advise for IPR management	Collection and commercialisation of the BioSuccinic Acid produced.	0
Subcontractor 2: AINIA (ES) strategic innovation partner		Technical assistance and analysis for the industrial unit implementation, support for commercialisation in South and Central EU	Market internationalization, dissemination to network of contacts (+700 companies & public bodies)	0

Figure 2 - NEOSUCCESS Partners & WP6 (D&C) effort

2.2 BRIEF PRESENTATION OF THE WORK PACKAGE 6 TASKS

The D&C Plan covers all the activities to be performed along the implementation of the WP6. The D&C Plan will cover, among others, the three tasks that make the WP6:

2.2.1 TASK 6.1 - DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

The main objectives of Task 6.1 are:

1. To build a NEOSUCCESS-related community that includes all relevant stakeholders and encourage long-term relations with potential clients.
2. Establish an easily recognizable NEOSUCCESS identity.
3. Raise awareness of NEOSUCCESS at national and international level.
4. To inform about NEOSUCCESS results and main outcomes to raise interest of potential key stakeholders.

Dissemination & Communication activities include: the NEOSUCCESS website (D6.2, M3) promotional video(s) (D6.1, M36), newsletters, press releases, publications, posters, roll ups, leaflets... and any other printed or online promotion material that is deemed necessary.

This task also includes all activities that are related to the participation at specialised events such as trade fairs, congresses, and summits related to main target sectors.

2.2.2 TASK 6.2 - DEMONSTRATION AND PROMOTIONAL ACTIVITIES

The industrial unit installed at IVEM's facilities will be used for the demonstration activities. Three demonstration sessions (M28, M31, M34) will be organized to raise awareness among the specific target groups (potential clients) about the technology and its benefits, and to ensure a successful market penetration of NEOSUCCESS.

2.2.3 TASK 6.3 - TRAINING ACTIVITIES

A series of 3 training activities (M28, M31, M34) focusing on the operational and wider socio-economic benefits of the developed technology will be prepared and delivered by AUTH and DTU to the technical and managerial staff from the industry and their members, end-users, and also to relevant actors beyond the consortium.

2.3 SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

The D&C Plan is the core document outlining the NEOSUCCESS' dissemination and communication activities. This plan is fundamental for a good coordination of all initiatives, defining the correct content of the messages, which should be adapted to each of the targeted audiences, getting the required D&C impact and effectively communicating the NEOSUCCESS results. Effective communication will encourage interested stakeholders to actively participate in the NEOSUCCESS and enhance the visibility of its results.

This Dissemination and Communication Plan aims to:

- Outline the main objectives of the dissemination and communication actions to be implemented along the 36 months of the NEOSUCCESS.
- Identify and describe the different groups of target audiences.
- Define the tools and channels to be used, the message and the activities required to reach each targeted audience(s).
- Effectively achieving and communicating the NEOSUCCESS' expected impacts.

2.4 GENERAL OBJECTIVES OF THE D&C PLAN

The D&C Plan has the following objectives:

- To set communications tools and protocols between the consortium partners.
- To promote the NEOSUCCESS among the public and relevant stakeholders within the selected target sectors.
- To guarantee a successful communication of the project key-messages and actions at Regional, National and EU level.
- To attract the interest of potential users for the NEOSUCCESS results and impacts, including opening potential business opportunities.

- To disseminate the NEOSUCCESS' results to a wider public.
- Set Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for dissemination activities.
- Implement measurement of the fulfilment of KPIs of the activities conducted.
- To promote collaboration and dialogue between the consortium partners, to increase the impact of the NEOSUCCESS and communicate it harmonically.

3. COMMUNICATION PROTOCOLS

Due to the diverse nature of the NEOSUCCESS community, different communication activities and channels, both electronic/online and face-to-face, will be exploited. Communication will happen at two distinct levels:

3.1 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

Internal communication will take place between partners and project collaborators. It is essential to set efficient internal communication channels and protocols for the project's proper outcome.

3.1.1 INTERNAL COMMUNICATIONS CHANNELS

- **Consortium face-to-face communications:** Ordinary meetings and Extraordinary meetings, if needed.

Due to current pandemic situation (COVID-19), the Consortium will take all necessary measures to ensure health security of its members. The Consortium will follow all the recommendation of World Health Organization (WHO) and EU Commission according to COVID-19 prevention procedures during face-to-face meetings.

(<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/advice-for-public>)

Furthermore, during the period of pandemic outbreak, the Consortium will try to perform all the communications in a non-presential way.

For example, the face-to-face Kick-Off Meeting (KOM) of the Project, scheduled in Valencia (Spain), took place through online platform.

- **Consortium online communications:** email, phone calls and video calls.

3.1.2 INTERNAL COMMUNICATIONS PROTOCOLS

Independently of the channel and members participating, every communication must be recorded, stored, and distributed among all the members of the Consortium. For this purpose, the following procedures must be taken:

- **Face-to-face communications:** each meeting should be documented in Minutes of Meeting (MoM). IVEM, as Project Coordinator, is in charge of elaborating and distributing them among all the consortium members via email. In the case that IVEM is not present at the meeting, the meeting organiser has to take care of this task. MoM should describe the events of the meeting, a list of attendees, a statement of the issues considered by Consortium Members, and related responses for the issues and actions to be implemented (with the action leader designed).

MoM should be sent to all the members not later than 7 days after the meeting took place. In the case that some member has any comments or amendments to MoM they should notify all other members within 7 days after the reception of MoM.

- **Consortium online communications:** The non-presential and oral communications (i.e. phone calls and video calls) should be documented in the same way as face-to-face communications (MoM). Additionally, they should be recorded by Project Coordinator or

the organiser (in the case that Project Coordinator is not attending). The record should be uploaded and made available for all consortium members.

3.2 EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION

External communication covers communication actions with:

- Key stakeholders actively involved with NEOSUCCESS and potential clients.
- General public, scientific community, policymakers, and external business professionals.
- Specific communication activities towards the EU Commission Services, e.g. email and phone calls with NEOSUCCESS officer, regular reports, deliverables, etc.

External communications channels will be discussed in detail in section 5: *DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIONS*.

All the COVID-19 health protection protocols and measures must be applied to minimize risks as in the case of internal communications.

4. TARGET AUDIENCES AND MESSAGES

This part of the deliverable is focused on defining the strengths of NEOSUCCESS project, the target audience, and the key messages to achieve its maximum dissemination through optimal communication channels.

4.1 NEOSUCCESS' MESSAGES: THE VALUE OF THE PROJECT

NEOSUCCESS Project has an immense value, it binds together and solves major problems of two separate sectors: Energy and Industrial Chemistry. On one hand, contribution to Renewable Energy Sources (RES) implementation with the biomethane production through the upgrading of the biogas, and on the other hand, greening the Industrial Chemistry with the production of a biobased and second-generation key bulk chemical, the BioSuccinic Acid.

4.1.1 ISSUE NR. 1: BIOMETHANE CHALLENGES

One of the biggest EU challenges for the next years is to replace the use of fossil fuels. There are several clearly defined paths for the fulfilment of this goal, one of them is to progressively **replace natural gas with renewable energy sources, such as biomethane, given its proven potential once upgraded from biogas.**

In Europe there are thousands of biogas plants, most of them focused on power generation through combustion of biogas in CHP (Combined Heat and Power) engines. To inject the biogas into natural gas network, CO₂ must be eliminated with upgrading process. However, this process is expensive, and has significant investment cost. It is important to note that many EU countries already have their legislation in place to support the biomethane injection.

4.1.2 ISSUE NR. 2: BIOSUCCINIC ACID CHALLENGES

BioSuccinic Acid is a building block which can be converted to a wide range of bio-based chemicals or materials, especially bioplastics. Currently, all the BioSuccinic Acid produced (accounting for the 5-10% of the overall production capacity) is of first-generation, so as it comes from agricultural food/crops feedstock. This means that its production requires use of natural resources that can be used in more efficient way or that directly competes with food. **The market urgently seeks for sustainable solutions that reduce the environmental impact.** It is the main objective of the second-generation biorefinery (biofuels, bioproducts) development.

4.1.3 THE SOLUTION: NEOSUCCESS SYNERGIES

NEOSUCCESS offers a cost-effective solution for the main challenges of biomethane and BioSA sectors at once.

On one hand, it offers a cost-effective technology that can help biomethane producers to fit into market prices or biogas producers to convert their facilities towards biomethane production. And, on the other hand, produces a second-generation BioSA from waste (agro-industrial residue streams) that can be of interest for the chemical industry.

However, there is an important difference between those two key commercial sectors. The industrial unit of NEOSUCCESS is intended to be part of biogas plants. Since one of the main inputs of the process is biogas, if BioSA producers want to buy and use NEOSUCCESS unit, they will need to have a biogas plant, which might be unlikely. The most likely scenario is the use of

the NEOSUCCESS unit in new or already installed biogas plants. Thus, the potential purchasers of the industrial unit of NEOSUCCESS are the biogas companies.

To ensure easy commercialization of the NEOSUCCESS industrial unit, we need to guarantee the commodities liquidity. NEOSUCCESS process produces biomethane and BioSA. Biogas sector is acquainted with biomethane, but BioSA is a brand-new product for them. They do not have any knowledge of this product (How to sell it? To whom? At what price?). Thus, different questions regarding the commercialization of this new commodity arise. To eliminate these possible fears and doubts, NEOSUCCESS aims to bring together the biogas/biomethane industries and BioSA buyers.

4.1.4 UNIQUE SELLING POINTS: MAIN GENERAL MESSAGES

The NEOSUCCESS Project main messages are:

- Cost-effective technology. It reduces biomethane (lowering upgrading expenses) and BioSA production costs.
- High productivity and efficiency.
- First technology worldwide that simultaneously targets BioSuccinic Acid and BioMethane.
- Easy implementation (*plug-and-play*) and different capacities adapted to client's needs.
- Sustainable and environmentally friendly process.
- CO₂ emission reductions, since CO₂ from biogas (already "green") is converted into a valuable chemical (not just removed from the inlet gas as in most of upgrading depuration processes).

4.2 TARGET AUDIENCES

Stakeholder mapping is an essential and basic step complementing the Dissemination and Communication activities of the NEOSUCCESS. There are 4 major target groups for the dissemination of the Project: Industrial and commercial sectors, general public, policy makers and academia.

As explained above, the two major industrial and commercial target sectors are biomethane and biosuccinic acid activities.

NORVENTO and IVEM already count with an established network of relevant contacts in the biomethane sector. IVEM is a wastewater treatment plant manager with biogas production and Norvento is an engineering and renewable energy sources developer, constructor, and has its own biogas division.

4.2.1 INDUSTRIAL PLAYERS FROM THE BIOMETHANE AND BIOSUCCINIC ACID SECTOR

This target audience is the key for commercialization of NEOSUCCESS Project. Biogas/biomethane and Succinic Acid industries are not easily prone to changes unless they have credible "industrial results". The industrial unit under scope within NEOSUCCESS project will act as an essential tool for the dissemination of the project and to convince potential clients.

As explained above, **the main potential end-client of the NEOSUCCESS industrial unit is the biomethane sector.** Considering the support of BioSA sector, it will be much easier to penetrate the biomethane market.

The main idea for future industrial commercialization of the NEOSUCCESS unit is to install it on biogas plants (producers of biomethane). There are two possible niches for business development which will be targeted as audiences of the D&C plan:

4.2.1.1 OPERATING BIOGAS PLANTS.

These plants are currently operating on a power generation model. NEOSUCCESS unit can help them to switch from electricity to biomethane production, thus offering them a cost-efficient solution. The key stakeholders are:

- Wastewater Treatment Plants
- Solid Waste Treatment Plants
- Agrofood industries
- Sugar Industries
- Livestock farms
- Bioethanol industries
- Biogas O&M¹ companies that are currently performing operation and maintenance at those facilities and can suggest to the owners the NEOSUCCESS option for better profitability of their business

4.2.1.2 NEW BIOGAS PLANTS.

In this case, the NEOSUCCESS unit can be included into the new biogas plant that stakeholders plan to build. This will improve overall expected revenues (adding BioSA as another income vector) and lower the upgrading costs. The potential clients are:

- Wastewater Treatment Plants
- Solid Waste Treatment Plants
- Agrofood Industries
- Sugar Industries
- Livestock farms
- Bioethanol industries
- Biogas/biomethane technological companies that might include NEOSUCCESS industrial unit as a part of their final biogas plant design offered to their end clients

4.2.1.3 CURRENT MAIN BIOMETHANE INDUSTRIES INFORMATION DEMANDS

The Biomethane industry is particularly interested in the information listed below:

- Industrial results (Technology Readiness Level)
- Costs (CAPEX and OPEX)
- Difficulty in operation and maintenance
- GHG emissions and carbon footprint of the technology
- Off taker of the Bio Succinic Acid

¹ O&M: Operation and Maintenance

- Liquidity of BioSuccinic Acid
 - How difficult is to sell the acid on the market?
 - Price changes
 - Size of the potential market

General message for the industrial players from the biomethane and biosuccinic acid sector: NEOSUCCESS is an alternative towards a more efficient and environmentally friendly solution for biomethane industries, since it entails lower carbon footprints along the process while making it more profitable for businesses.

NEOSUCCESS addresses the main questions of the biomethane sector through strong involvement with the BioSuccinic Acid sector, thus boosting business opportunities in both industries.

4.2.2 GENERAL PUBLIC: COMMUNITIES, CIVIL SOCIETY NETWORKS

The General Public is a direct beneficiary of the NEOSUCCESS: (i) production of renewable energy (biomethane) as direct substitute of natural gas and (ii) production of BioSuccinic Acid that can replace fossil-based platform chemicals, both using as raw material (feedstock) agri-food industry waste. The general public main concerns that NEOSUCCESS aims to answer are:

- Society is demanding information on GHG emissions/Global Warming.
- Society is demanding information on actions taken by the EU.
- Society is demanding information on waste production of industries.
- Society is demanding information about the renewable energies.

By disseminating and informing the general society, NEOSUCCESS will raise awareness on the importance of different industrial environmental problems: An informed society can lead significant changes in the industry if they demand products that are respectful of the environment.

General message for the General Public: NEOSUCCESS helps biomethane/biogas sector to be more competitive and replace the use of natural gas. NEOSUCCESS uses waste streams to produce renewable gas.

4.2.3 POLICY MAKERS: GOVERNMENTS AND EU

One of the main objectives of the NEOSUCCESS respond to the “The European Green Deal” plan of the EU in relation to EU's greenhouse gas emission reductions target for 2030 to at least 50% and towards 55% (compared with 1990 levels) and climate neutrality in 2050. NEOSUCCESS aim to substitute fuel-based energy sources (mainly natural gas) by improving biomethane production economic feasibility and producing second-generation Biosuccinic acid by using waste as raw material.

General message for the policy makers: NEOSUCCESS supports efficient and environmentally friendly solutions that follow the current EU policies.

4.2.4 ACADEMIA: ACADEMICS AND RESEARCHERS

Research actors (both private and public) create knowledge and promote innovation in the industry. For that reason, the academia will also be a target of the NEOSUCCESS technology. Experts, academics, and researchers will be informed about NEOSUCCESS outcomes and the environmental concerns of industry and the EU.

General message for the academy: NEOSUCCESS supports research on efficient, innovative, and environmentally friendly solutions for the industry.

4.3 SPECIFIC MESSAGES BY TARGET AUDIENCE

It is particularly important to fit the dissemination key messages into the needs of the stakeholders. The project must answer all the questions that might arise in this sense. The transmitted message must be brief and precise, solving all the doubts at once and convincing the audience of the NEOSUCCESS benefits. Additionally, it is essential to adapt the messages of NEOSUCCESS to its different target audiences.

The table below shows a preliminary list of key message lines for each target audience:

TARGET AUDIENCE	MESSAGES
BIOMETHANE SECTOR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial proven technology (First technology worldwide that simultaneously targets biomethane and BioSA). • Proven results. • High quality and quantity: (>95% biomethane) & (>80% BioSA). • Cost-effective technology. Production costs of the biomethane produced with NEOSUCCESS technology are 50% lower than current alternatives. • Easy implementation (<i>plug-and-play</i>). • Scalable. Capacities adapted to client's needs. • Environmentally Friendly. Upgrading process with use of CO₂ for BioSA production (CO₂ is fixed in BioSA). • Great BioSA market. Supported by BioSA off takers.
BIOSUCCINIC ACID MARKET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • World's first-of-a-kind second-generation technology to produce BioSuccinic Acid • Unique and patented biomass-based process. • Sustainable and safe biological process.
GENERAL PUBLIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmentally friendly. • Reduction of CO₂ emissions of industries. • Sustainable. Use of waste to produce biomethane that substitutes fossil fuels. Use of CO₂ for production of BioSuccinic Acid that substitutes current fossil fuels-based solutions. • Use of EU Funds to fight Global Warming. • Supports the transition of the EU energy sector; introduces advanced technology to improve competitiveness. • Use of organic waste to generate renewable gas that is a substitute of natural gas.

POLICY MAKERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology that follows EU policies. • Technology that helps to substitute fossil fuels by renewable energy.
ACADEMIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and development tested and proven on industrial scale. • Strong support of EU institution for innovation.

Throughout the NEOSUCCESS project duration the feedback from this target audiences will be gathered. The Consortium will adapt the dissemination messages to fit in and improve the impact of the communication and dissemination plan.

5. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

The Dissemination & Communication actions will use both Online and Offline channels.

5.1 ONLINE CHANNELS

5.1.1 THE NEOSUCCESS WEBSITE

Webpage address: <https://neosuccess-project.eu> (Deliverable D6.1).

The NEOSUCCESS Project website was launched on M3 of the project (August 2020), as scheduled in the description of the WP6 of the GA. The webpage will be active during the NEOSUCCESS Project execution and it will be maintained for at least five years after the end of the NEOSUCCESS Project. The webpage is designed for two different audience groups:

- i) General public with general information of the project.
- ii) Specialized audience with technical information.

5.1.1.1 GENERAL STRUCTURE OF THE WEBPAGE

The site map is structured as follows:

- A) The Project:
 - a. Description
 - b. Objectives
 - c. Activities
 - d. Results
- B) Members of the consortium (Brief description of the members, their logo and link to their webpage):
 - a. Participants (4 Consortium Partners)
 - b. Third Parties (2 Subcontractors)
- C) Links (Interesting links related to the NEOSUCCESS project).
- D) News and events (Information on project progress and events).
- E) Dissemination (Public documents will be accessible in the NEOSUCCESS website through this page. This may include NEOSUCCESS deliverables, online training activity tool, newsletters, or press releases).
- F) Contact (Contact of Project Coordinator, IVEM).

The web will be updated as NEOSUCCESS starts producing new results and outcomes.

5.1.1.2 NOTES ON THE WEBPAGE CONTENT

- Any update of the content must be approved by NEOSUCCESS Communication Commission (according to 6.1: COMMUNICATION COMMISSION).
- The webpage includes links to social media of NEOSUCCESS.
- The webpage includes Information on EU funding and Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility according to articles 29.4 and 29.5 of Grant Agreement No 950921.
- The first version of the webpage is available in English. During the duration of the project it will be translated and published in Spanish. Once the NEOSUCCESS business plan is drafted and target countries are finally selected, the partners will decide a third official EU language to translate the webpage to, presumably German (as indicated in the GA).

Additionally, **a general description of NEOSUCCESS should be created in all partners websites and linked to project official website.** This information must include EU funding visibility.

KPI (Key Performance Indicator): 1,000 yearly visits.

5.1.2 AUDIO VISUAL MATERIALS

NEOSUCCESS will produce two promotional videos:

1. A short clip (2-3') to raise awareness on sustainable BioSuccinic Acid and BioMethane production.
2. At the end of the project, a longer video with interviews of project partners, showing the Demo Unit and explaining the project's main outcomes, results, and benefits.

The videos will be uploaded on the official website. **Target for the videos:** 500 views.

5.1.3 NEWSLETTERS

For each newsletter release, the Communication Commission will appoint the Partner that will oversee its drafting. Unless some Consortium member propose itself, the Communication Commission will assign different Partner each time. It will be written periodically to keep all relevant stakeholders informed of the NEOSUCCESS activity and results.

Target for the promotional newsletters: approximately, biannually (twice per year).

5.1.4 SOCIAL MEDIA (LINKEDIN / TWITTER / YOUTUBE)

One of the simplest access means for project information dissemination is social media. It is a tool for fast spread of news and outcomes across diverse target groups.

Social media has a double purpose: communicating and disseminating.

1. General project news, attendance to congresses, consortium meetings and posts on the overall development of the project will be actions for communication targeted on the general public and a more heterogenous audience.
2. Publishing of results will be a dissemination action targeted to wide-ranging but specific audience (scientific community).

Among different online platforms, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube are one of the most suitable for dissemination of NEOSUCCESS Project.

5.1.4.1 TWITTER

Twitter is an online platform focused on general public that allows the project to reach the global audience. It is one of the biggest social networks focused on fast, concise, and direct form of spreading the information.

The official hashtag used of the project will be *#ProjectNEOSUCCESS*. It must be followed by Horizon 2020 hashtag *#EU_H2020*.

Target for Twitter: 200 followers.

5.1.4.2 LINKEDIN

LinkedIn is a business orientated service where skilled audience (people and companies) attends to obtain more professional information and news. This platform will be used to reach potential clients from selected target sectors.

The LinkedIn account will be opened as a “Product Page”.

Target for LinkedIn: 200 followers.

5.1.4.3 YOUTUBE

YouTube account will be created as a main tool for promotional video dissemination. It will also be used to publish any other video recorded by the partners.

Target for YouTube: 500 views per video published.

5.1.4.4 SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT

NORVENTO will manage the Twitter and the LinkedIn accounts of NEOSUCCESS: building, growing, and managing the created online community. NORVENTO will develop tailored messages for each social media account, considering its differences in structure and tagging systems.

The NEOSUCCESS project will be mentioned on a regular basis on general communication messages (project goals, potential impact, project partners, challenges...etc); project events and updates (General Assemblies, congresses, trade shows...) and project results (when available). NEOSUCCESS releases will use a friendly tone and will always be respectful with its audiences.

5.2 OFFLINE CHANNELS

Offline channels are important for direct communication and dissemination of the project, allowing closer contact and easier face-to-face communication with stakeholders.

5.2.1 TRADE SHOWS, CONGRESSES AND SUMMITS

NEOSUCCESS Consortium aims to attend to several congresses and summits. It is of key strategical importance to assist to world-known events to establish initial contact with potential clients, receive feedback from target sectors and adapt the communication and dissemination plan to improve commercial diffusion of the project. It will also help to improve our business network and to introduce NEOSUCCESS as a highly interesting solution.

We expect to attend to **trade shows** and summits of great interest for the promotion of NEOSUCCESS. The following are some events where we would like to participate:

- **The World Biogas Summit.** (<http://world-biogas-summit.com/>) Global thought-leadership forum for the AD (anaerobic digestion) and biogas industry.
- **Bio 360 Expo** (formerly known as Biogaz Europe) (<https://www.bio-360.com/en/>) Bio360 brings together the entire biogas sector, attracts 7.000 visitors and 450 exhibitors from 35 countries.
- **CO2 Reuse Summit** (<https://reuseco2.com/>) The conference gathers major players from the industry to highlight the latest developments related to carbon utilization.
- **World Biomaterials Congress** (<https://wbc2020.org/>) This congress provides a global forum for biomaterials companies and professionals to share their knowledge, discover insights, network, and discuss trending topics.
- **The World Biogas EXPO 2020** (<http://www.biogastradeshows.com/>). The Largest International Trade Show Solely Dedicated to Anaerobic Digestion and Biogas.

Other examples:

- Biogas Expo & Congress
- European Association of Agricultural Economists Congress

Consortium Members will attend to trade fairs, congresses, and summits as the ones above. One of their main tasks during these events will be the presentation of NEOSUCCESS to possible clients. It is vital to collect as many feedbacks as possible from key audience sectors. With this information the Consortium can adjust the message to their needs and update the D&C Plan.

It is important to choose wisely not only the events to attend to, but also in which stage of the project it should be done. One of the key elements for the success of the project dissemination is to give firm results. The industrial unit must be built and produce satisfactory outcomes. The Communication Commission should be notified by Partners their wish to attend any other event.

Target for trade shows, congresses, and conferences: at least 4.

5.2.2 NEOSUCCESS DEMONSTRATION ACTIVITIES

To involve its target audiences more actively in discussion on the theory and methodology development and applications of the NEOSUCCESS technology, the NEOSUCCESS Consortium will organise a series of 3 Demonstration activities among potential clients (Task 6.2). The initial calendar and target stakeholders for these workshops are:

5.2.2.1 1st SESSION (ABOUT M28)

The 1st session will be carried out by IVEM at M28 (approx.), at which the target audience will be the Biogas industries across EU and worldwide. In this session the industrial unit will be presented. This session is focused on biomethane sector and must solve all the questions or doubts that might arise. It is important to highlight the following features of NEOSUCCESS industrial unit:

- Technology readiness level: Proven results on industrial scale.
- Quality and quantity of end products (biomethane and BioSA).

- Cost-effectiveness: Investment and Operation Costs.
- Easiness of operation.

Attendants expected: at least 15.

5.2.2.2 2nd SESSION (ABOUT M31)

This session will target the sugar industry and the chemical industry, where also actors already in the BioSuccinic Acid market will be invited.

Attendants expected: at least 12.

5.2.2.3 3rd SESSION (ABOUT M34)

The last session will be an open demonstration event. MEDIA and PRESS will be invited, as well as other stakeholders and end-users not identified yet. The 3rd session will be recorded, and the video will be streamed via NEOSUCCESS project website, which will ensure that the impact and scope of the demonstration activities are heightened.

An interactive discussion will follow the demonstration, whereby the socioeconomic, safety and quality benefits derived using the technology will be presented and discussed. Comments and feedback from the attendees will be sought.

The content of all the sessions will be published on the website of NEOSUCCESS.

Attendants expected: at least 20.

5.2.3 NEOSUCCESS TRAINING ACTIVITIES

A comprehensive series of 3 training activities (M28, M31, M34) focusing on the operational and wider socio-economic benefits of the developed technology will be prepared and delivered by AUTH and DTU to the technical and managerial staff from the industry and their members, end-users, and also to relevant actors beyond the consortium. The aim of these training sessions will be to educate participants on the technical and operational aspects of NEOSUCCESS, as well as on the competitive and socio-economic benefits. These training sessions will facilitate understanding, acceptance and future uptake and exploitation of the results of this project by the members of the industry and stakeholders' participants.

The training sessions will take place in parallel with the demonstration sessions (Task 6.3). To widen further the impact of the training effort beyond the consortium, an on-line training tool will be developed and embedded into the project website.

Target for trainings: 3 activities.

5.3 MIXED CHANNELS

Mixed channels cover actions that can take place at both online and offline levels.

5.3.1 PRESS RELEASES:

Regular press releases will be issued, coinciding with important events and NEOSUCCESS milestones. Press releases will be published in English and Spanish.

Target for press releases: at least 1 press release per year is expected.

5.3.2 D&C MATERIALS:

The NEOSUCCESS Dissemination materials include brochures, leaflets, roll ups, posters, and any other visual printed material that NEOSUCCESS requires throughout its execution. The content of the materials will be in English and will be tailored according their specific size, structure, and target audience.

As a baseline, all dissemination materials will always include:

- Name, slogan, and logo of NEOSUCCESS.
- NEOSUCCESS duration (Start and end date)
- GA Number
- EU Funding mention and corresponding logo. (KEY)
- Name and location of the NEOSUCCESS coordinator and that of the NEOSUCCESS partners.
- Contact information: NEOSUCCESS coordinator and communication partner.
- NEOSUCCESS main goals and messages.

All dissemination materials will be available in printed and online versions (in the Dissemination section of the webpage). The consortium should also design promotional stand and flyers for NEOSUCCESS to be used by our team at the different fairs.

Target for D&C materials: at least 5 different materials.

5.3.3 PUBLICATIONS AND ARTICLES

NEOSUCCESS will produce articles targeted at the different audiences identified in this D&C plan. The content of publications and articles will be defined by the project partners, which includes the type of information and publication to be used to address the scientific community, the industry (for example, Specialist magazines publications), the policy makers or the general public.

DTU and AUTH will be in charge for publications at scientific journals.

Target for scientific publications: at least 1 scientific publication during the project lifespan.

5.4 PARTNERS DISSEMINATION ACTIONS

Each of the consortium partners is an essential tool for project dissemination. They are renowned and working organizations that have already established their own dissemination instruments.

Most of them have regular newsletters, blogs, and press releases. They can be used as launch pad for NEOSUCCESS Project dissemination. The diffusion of any activities published by NEOSUCCESS project can be multiplied by consortium partners.

Each of the consortium partners should use their own communication and dissemination channels for NEOSUCCESS Project broadcasting.

Any event (congress, trade fair, summit, presentation, etc.) regarding NEOSUCCESS with presence of Consortium partner should be registered through photos, videos, press notes, etc.

5.5 SUMMARY OF THE TARGETS FOR THE D&C ACTIONS

In summary the main dissemination actions for the project are:

Online channels	Target audience	Target description	Target number
Webpage	All audiences	Web active since M3 of the NEOSUCCESS. Content updated	1,000 visits/year
Audio visual materials	All audiences	Production of 2 informative videos	500 views
Newsletters	Industry, academia, policy makers	Periodic newsletters with relevant news and updates of the NEOSUCCESS	Twice a year
Social media Twitter	General audiences	Engagement with the general audiences and its concerns. Production of visual attractive content tailored to the platform.	200 followers
Social media LinkedIn	Industry, academia, policy makers	Engagement with the Industry, academia, policy makers and its concerns. Production of visual attractive content tailored to the platform.	200 followers
Social media YouTube	All audiences	Dissemination of NEOSUCCESS' audio visual materials	500 views per video
Offline channels	Target audience	Target description	Target number
Trade shows & Fairs, Congresses, Summits	Industry (Biomethane and BioSA)	Participation in relevant trade shows. For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The World Biogas Summit. Bio 360 Expo (formerly known as CO2 Reuse Summit) World Biomaterials Congress The World Biogas EXPO 2020 	4
NEOSUCCESS Demonstrations sessions	Industry, academia, policy makers	Demonstration Sessions organised by NEOSUCCESS. These events will help disseminate the project and its results	3
NEOSUCCESS Training sessions	Industry, academia, policy makers	Training Sessions organised by NEOSUCCESS. These events will help disseminate NEOSUCCESS and its results. (Organised in parallel with Demonstration sessions).	3
Mixed channels	Target audience	Target description	Target number
Press Releases	All audiences	NEOSUCCESS will publish press releases to inform of the progress and milestones of NEOSUCCESS	1 per year
D&C Materials	All audiences	D&C materials included tailored designs for: Leaflets, Posters, Roll ups, the NEOSUCCESS summary document and the Promotional Stand	5 different materials designed
Scientific publications	Industry, academia, policy makers	Scientific journals	1 publication

6. CONSORTIUM COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND OBLIGATIONS

The Consortium must ensure correct application of D&C Plan, follow the guidelines given, use the standardized tools, protect the data and confidential information. NEOSUCCESS project counts with an important EU funding which should be visible during the project dissemination.

6.1 COMMUNICATION COMMISSION

NEOSUCCESS will create a Communication Commission to take care of the data management of NEOSUCCESS. This Commission will also decide which documents will be made public and private to avoid the dissemination of any potential confidential information.

NEOSUCCESS's data protection policy will ensure that any personal data is treated according to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Each Consortium Partner will appoint one person of its organization as the member of this commission.

Additionally, it will also watch over the correct use of NEOSUCCESS visual identity and EU Funding Visibility.

6.2 VISIBILITY OF FUNDING

According to the Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement of the NEOSUCCESS project:

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 950921

EU logos files (.eps, .pdf, .jpg) and details on how to acknowledge EU funding can be found at: <https://ec.europa.eu/inea/en/connecting-europe-facility/cef-energy/beneficiaries-info-point/publicity-guidelines-logos>

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

6.2.1 SOCIAL MEDIA: DATA MANAGEMENT AND MENTION OF FUNDING

NEOSUCCESS project is strongly focused on Confidentiality of its results, thus the social media moderators can only disseminate the outcomes that have been already published on the project

official webpage. Any other dissemination of the results must be approved by NEOSUCCESS Communication Commission (according to 6.1: COMMUNICATION COMMISSION).

According to article 29.4 of Grant Agreement No 950921 both social media should include relevant information acknowledging EU Funding in the official profile description and in any communication. This information must include at least EU emblem and the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 950921”*.

However, according to “EU Grants: H2020 Guidance — Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects: V1.1 – 07.01.2020²” in the case of Twitter the exception can be made. The recommended text for Twitter profile information is:

“This project receives funding from the @EU_H2020 Research & Innovation Programme. Any related tweets reflect only the views of the project owner.”

The social media managers should use after mentioned EU social media guide as support tool for their task.

6.3 NEOSUCCESS’ VISUAL IDENTITY

An easily recognisable (visual) identity of the NEOSUCCESS project is essential to achieve best communication results. It is of high importance to use these visual tools coherently.

6.3.1 NEOSUCCESS LOGO

NEOSUCCESS logo is the main recognition tool for the branding:

6.3.1.1 NEOSUCCESS FULL LOGO

This full logo should be used in all the documents. The minimum length of the logo should be 55 mm. Any use of the logo below this dimension will make the smaller text impossible to read.

6.3.1.2 NEOSUCCESS REDUCED LOGO

In the cases in which due to specifics of the use it is impossible to achieve the minimal length of the logo, the reduced logo should be used:

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

6.3.1.3 NEOSUCCESS ICON

For special purposes when the logo has to fit in a specific shape some variation of the logo can be used. For example, for Twitter profile image, recommended dimensions are 400x400 (square shape):

6.3.2 NEOSUCCESS FONTS AND COLOURS

The typography and colours chosen for branding of NEOSUCCESS are:

- **Font: Exo 2 (Semi-bold 600)**

Sample:

“LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECTETUR ADIPISCING ELIT, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.”

Link for its download:

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Exo+2?sidebar.open&selection.family=Exo+2:wght@600#standard-styles>

License Note: These fonts are licensed under the Open Font License. You can use them freely in your products & projects - print or digital, commercial, or otherwise. However, you cannot sell the fonts on their own.

- **Main Branding Colours:**

6.4 TEMPLATES

NEOSUCCESS created special templates to use them for newsletter, press releases, scientific conference presentations, policy briefs, papers, presentations, etc. to unify the aspect in which our communications are released. The standardization of the dissemination tools is essential to provide solid brand image for potential clients.

The templates are available for all the members. Any changes applied must be consulted and approved by Communication Commission.

6.4.1 PRESENTATION TEMPLATE:

6.4.2 DOCUMENT TEMPLATE:

7. FOLLOWING STEPS

The following steps in Dissemination and Communication Plan involve:

1. Creation of Communication Commission.
2. Creation of social media accounts (Twitter and LinkedIn).
3. Design of NEOSUCCESS promotional material (stands, flyers).
4. Measurement of D&C main KPIs fulfilment (annex).
5. Active control on D&C Plan compliance by all partners.

8. UPDATE OF THE D&C Plan

This document will be updated with the Deliverables 6.3 “First year of D&C Plan implementation” by M12 and the D6.4 “Final report on D&C activities” by M36.

9. ANNEXES

9.1 MEASURING RESULTS TABLE

NEOSUCCESS will use the table of the point 5.4 to measure numerically the progress and impact of the communication of the NEOSUCCESS project. Target numbers will be reviewed every 6 months by Communication Commission to assess future communication actions.

Online channels	Target number	M6	M9	M12	M15	M18	M21	M24	M27	M30	M33	M36
Webpage	1,000 visits/ year											
NEOSUCCESS video	2 videos; 500 views											
Newsletters	2 per year (total 6)											
Social media Twitter	200 followers											
Social media LinkedIn	200 followers											
Social media YouTube	500 views per video											
Offline channels	Target number	M6	M9	M12	M15	M18	M21	M24	M27	M30	M33	M36
Trade shows & Fairs	4											
Demonstration Session	3											
Training Session	3											
Mixed channels	Target number	M6	M9	M12	M15	M18	M21	M24	M27	M30	M33	M36
Press Releases	1 per year (total 3)											
D&C Materials	5 different materials designed											
Scientific publications	1											